

Renewable Energy Sources: An educational approach in Greek Schools

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10149031

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Abstract. In this article we introduce the educational scenario titled “Renewable Energy Sources” which has been developed within the framework of the Connect project. We outline the implementation of this educational scenario in Greek schools and describe the pedagogical approach that students have engaged with. Furthermore, we highlight the key outcomes resulting from this implementation. Our findings strongly indicate that this scenario significantly enhances students’ confidence in science.

1. Introduction

Over the past three years we have actively participated in the Connect project, a European project that is dedicated to open schooling and participatory science [1]. Open Schooling purpose is to establish purposeful collaborations between educational institutions and their broader communities. This approach involves engaging families, experts, and various stakeholders in partnership with teachers and students. The goal is to address relevant local challenges, and promote a global citizenship mindset. The Connect project is designed to empower educators and schools to embrace open schooling in the core of the curriculum and basic aim is to increase the science capital for each student. We decided to design an educational scenario where the main objective was to investigate the environmental advantages of utilization of renewable energy sources (RES) instead of the combustion of fossil fuels. In this study we present the three phases of the RES educational scenario and also we refer to the important elements of Connect project that is to involve the family of the students as well as students to be guided and inspired from scientists. Among the pedagogical phases we present the android application which is developed especially for the RES educational scenario. Additionally, we show how other schools of Greece implemented this specific didactic approach. Finally we discuss the opportunities that arise for our students and what are the main advantages for them.

2. Phases of the scenario

The educational scenarios that are implemented through Connect project are developed used on the pedagogical frame of the three phases: Care, Know, Do. These three phases have been proposed as a basis for an open school didactic approach [2]. The RES educational scenario is designed to be performed in the Physics class of the third grade in Greek Junior High school, in the chapter of electrical energy [3]. It deals with the real problem of the pollution of the environment arised from the energy combustion plants. Especially in the island of Crete in Greece where our students live, there are three energy plants of this type producing about 70% of the electrical energy used [4], therefore they face the problem of pollution every day.

2.1. Care phase

In the first phase students were informed about the real problem through a video of the University of Macedonia of Greece where they could observe the journey of the electric energy and the consequences of the pollution from energy combustion plants. Then they discussed the problem with their families by completing a questionnaire. Subsequently, students engaged in a comprehensive classroom discussion. Due to the COVID restrictions students played an electronic escape room game designed by the first author. Students awareness is a very important element in this phase in order to motivate them. Students also show care about the environment and think alternative ways for energy consumption. Simultaneously students develop responsibility and ethical values that are important elements to become responsible citizens. Their families play a crucial role by recognizing that their children are dynamical individuals and that can think solutions to real and open problems of the society. Connect project not only gives the framework in the learning process but also connects family with the school. Family members support and encourage students while through collaboration give positive reinforcement and boost student's confidence.

2.2. Know phase

In the second phase students explore the real problem using the android application "Energy Consumption". This application was developed especially for the Connect project by the second author, and it is possible to download it from Google Play (figure1). Students download the application in their devices and then calculate the energy consumption with their parents and discuss their findings in the class. This activity help students to realize that they can reduce the energy consumption in their houses. Afterwards students think and discuss the questions that pose in an expert scientist. The scientist is a professor in the Hellenic Mediterranean University and is specialized in photovoltaic systems. In this phase students develop the critical thinking, technological skills as well as communication and collaboration skills.

https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=appinventor.ai_chalkia_duck.EnergyConsumption&pli=1

Figure 1. The android application "Energy Consumption"

2.3. Do phase

In the last phase students working in pairs designing a poster and build a STEM construction with two small photovoltaic panels. Additionally during this last phase students discuss in the class what they have done, reflect upon the problem, propose solutions and conclude. Creativity and innovation are

developed in this stage and students create something that is meaningful and impactful for them and for their families.

3. Other schools

This training scenario was created during the first year of the "Connect" project, alongside some other training scenarios created by colleagues. During the next two years of the project, colleagues from schools entering the project were able to choose one of these or create a new scenario of their own. The Renewable Energy Sources scenario was chosen by 25 other educators making it one of the most popular scenarios among teachers. They used the android application as well as the questionnaires and the escape game. Moreover, they adapted it in their local needs and then implemented it in their classes. Many of these schools participated in the Greek student conference of Connect and they had the opportunity to disseminate their work. Furthermore, each educator choosed scientists from the Greek Universities, specialized in renewable sources (i.e. wind energy, geothermal energy, photovoltaic systems etc) to discuss with students and answer their questions.

4. Conclusions

The Connect project has brought significant benefits for students, forstering a transformative educational experience. One of the advantages lies in the observed enthusiasm among students. Furthermore, the involvement of families and the integration of scientists into the educational process have enriched the students' learning enviromnent. Students within Connect are better equipped to contribute to sustainable solutions, making a positive impact on their communities and beyond. But apart from the general characteristics of the Connect project, it is worth sharing some thoughts and experiences from the implementation of our own scenario, as well as from the discussion with colleagues who have chosen and implemented it with their students.

The success and popularity of an open schooling activity depends on two important key points, the first concerning students and families and the second concerning educators. The active or non-active participation of pupils and their families in open schooling activities is directly related to the subject of the activity. The issue of energy consumption and renewable energy sources suddenly became a hot topic in everyday life after the outbreak of the war in Ukraine and its impact on Europe's gas supply. Moreover, the choice of implementing a scenario or not depends on the teacher. In an educational system, such as the Greek one, with an inflexible curriculum, the second factor relates to the ease with which it is integrated into the course syllabus. Our scenario is implemented easily through the Greek curriculum. In conclusion, we believe that our scenario fulfills both two important key points.

5. References

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